

Identification of Efficiency and Acceptance of New Vaccinations in Children: A Sentiment-Based Analysis

Merin Joseph
PG scholar
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally,India
merinjoseph2023b@mca.ajce.in

Dr.Bijimol TK
Asst. Professor
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally,India
tkbijimol@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—The successful implementation of new vaccines for children requires not only their efficiency but also public acceptance and sentiment towards them. In this paper, we present a sentiment analysis of feedback from parents and guardians of children who have received the COVID-19 vaccine. Using a rule-based approach with the SentimentIntensityAnalyzer from the Natural Language Toolkit, we analyzed comments collected from a website to identify the public's sentiment towards the COVID-19 vaccine in children, including concerns about its safety and effectiveness. Our analysis showed that the majority of feedback was positive, with parents expressing relief and confidence in the vaccine's safety and effectiveness. However, a minor portion of comments expressed worries about the vaccine's side effects and long-term impacts. Our findings provide valuable insights into the public's sentiment towards the COVID-19 vaccine in children and can inform healthcare authorities and policymakers in their efforts to increase vaccine uptake and address public concerns. This analysis serves as a test case for using sentiment analysis to evaluate the efficiency and acceptance of new vaccines in children.

Keywords—Machine learning, Covid-19, Sentimental Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most efficient approaches to fight the COVID-19 virus has emerged: vaccination. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a wide range of effects on people. In order to achieve herd immunity and stop the virus from spreading, vaccination of children is becoming more and more important, even though vaccines were initially created for and given to adults. Parents and other carers have expressed conflicting opinions regarding the vaccination procedure and its results since vaccination in youngsters has sparked their worries and anxieties.

In this paper, we present a sentiment analysis of COVID-19 vaccination in children based on feedback analysis. Our goal is to investigate the feelings and perspectives of parents and other adults who provide care for children concerning the COVID-19 immunization and to offer insights into the variables that affect their attitudes towards vaccination. We seek to provide a thorough understanding of the attitudes towards the COVID-19 immunization of children by analyzing input from a vaccination website.

Four of the most common COVID-19 vaccines given to kids will be the subject of our analysis: Covishield-dose1,

Covaxin, Covishield-dose2, and Sputnik V. The response will be analysed using natural language processing techniques to determine the sentiment and emotions conveyed, as well as the most prevalent themes and issues related to childhood COVID-19 immunisation.

The insights from our analysis can be used to inform policymakers, healthcare professionals, and other stakeholders about the concerns and apprehensions of parents and caregivers regarding COVID-19 vaccination in children. Our findings can also help to design effective communication strategies that address the concerns and build confidence in the safety and efficacy of COVID-19 vaccines for children

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Szilagyi et al. (2021) carried out a survey[1] to discover out more almost how guardians of kids between the ages of 12 and 15 feel around the COVID-19 vaccination. The consider found that guardians who bolstered both sides of the immunization wrangle about were concerned almost the vaccine's viability, security, and conceivable long-term impacts on their children's wellbeing.

Liao et al.'s evaluation of studies on vaccine reluctance during the COVID-19 pandemic was published in 2021[2]. According to the analysis, a number of variables, including social media, false information, and mistrust of healthcare systems, contributed to vaccine hesitancy.

Overall, these studies highlight the need to understand public sentiment and opinions towards COVID-19 vaccination in children, as this information can help healthcare professionals and policymakers address concerns and improve vaccine uptake rates.

Several studies have examined the sentiment of parents and caregivers towards COVID-19 vaccination for their children.

A cross-sectional study was undertaken in Jordan to look into people's acceptance of and attitudes towards COVID-19 vaccines. El-Elimat et al. (2021) publish their findings in the publication "Acceptance and attitudes towards COVID-19 vaccines: A cross-sectional study from Jordan"[3]. A sample of 2,412 trial participants responded to an online questionnaire that inquired about their views on immunisation, whether they had gotten the COVID-19 vaccine, and the reasons behind their reluctance to do so.

Watson et al.'s mathematical modelling study, published in *The Lancet* in March 2022, aimed to estimate the global impact of COVID-19 vaccination[4] during the first year of vaccine rollout. The authors used a transmission model to estimate the number of COVID-19 cases, hospitalizations, and deaths that could be averted by different vaccination scenarios.

This paper presents a study on sentiment analysis and subject distillation from Twitter data related to COVID-19 vaccines[5]. The authors used machine learning techniques to analyze tweets and extract sentiment and topics related to COVID-19 vaccines. The study found that the sentiment towards COVID-19 vaccines is generally positive, with the majority of tweets expressing support for vaccination. However, there were also concerns and criticisms expressed in some tweets, particularly around issues such as vaccine efficacy, side effects, and distribution. The study also identified several topics related to COVID-19 vaccines, including vaccine development, vaccine distribution, and vaccine efficacy. Overall, the study provides insights into public attitudes towards COVID-19 vaccines and highlights the importance of monitoring and understanding social media discussions around vaccination.

"Fine-tuned Sentiment Analysis of COVID-19 Vaccine-Related Social Media Data[6]: Comparative Study" by Melton et al.:

Melton et al. conducted a comparative study of sentiment analysis approaches on COVID-19 vaccine-related social media data. The authors utilized fine-tuning of pre-trained language models and evaluated their performance against lexicon-based approaches. The study found that fine-tuning approaches outperformed lexicon-based approaches in terms of overall accuracy and positive/negative sentiment classification. The authors concluded that deep learning-based sentiment analysis can provide a more accurate and efficient method for analyzing large-scale social media data related to COVID-19 vaccines.

III. MOTIVATION

Understanding the perceptions and attitudes of parents about immunising their children against COVID-19 is the inspiration behind sentiment analysis of COVID-19 vaccination in children. As the epidemic continues to harm people all over the world, immunising children is crucial to halting the virus's spread. There aren't many statistics on parents' views on immunising their kids, which could affect vaccination rates. We can therefore learn more about parents' concerns, preferences, and attitudes concerning the COVID-19 vaccination of children by examining their comments. This information can help policymakers and healthcare professionals make informed decisions on vaccine distribution and education strategies to increase vaccination rates in children.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In summary, building a sentiment analysis model for the sentiment graph involves data collection, data preprocessing, feature extraction, model selection, model

training and evaluation, sentiment graph generation, model optimization, and a conclusion. By following these steps, you can build an accurate and robust sentiment analysis model that can effectively analyze user feedback data and generate insightful sentiment graphs.

1.Data Collection: Collect Covid-19 vaccine feedback data from a reliable source such as social media platforms or vaccine review websites. Ensure that the data is properly labeled with the sentiment (positive, negative, or neutral).

2.Data Preprocessing: Preprocess the data by cleaning and formatting the feedback text. This may involve removing stop words, punctuation, and other noise. Also, perform data normalization and standardization to ensure consistency.

3.Feature Extraction: Extract relevant features from the feedback data that can help the sentiment analysis model distinguish between positive, negative, and neutral sentiments. Some commonly used features are Bag of Words (BoW), Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), and Word Embeddings.

4.Model Selection: Select a suitable machine learning model for sentiment analysis. The code employs the `SentimentIntensityAnalyzer`, a lexicon-based model that has already been trained, from the `Natural Language Toolkit` (`nltk`) library. As an alternative, Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are a few well-liked models for sentiment analysis.

5.Model Training and Evaluation: Train and evaluate the selected model on a labeled dataset and adjust the model parameters as needed to improve its performance. For the code provided, this step is skipped as the `SentimentIntensityAnalyzer` is a pre-trained model.

6.Sentiment Graph Generation: Use the selected model to generate sentiment scores for each Covid-19 vaccine based on the feedback data. Plot the sentiment scores for each vaccine on a graph using a suitable visualization tool such as `Matplotlib`. The code provided does this by calculating the average sentiment polarity for each vaccine and plotting it on a bar graph.

7.Model Optimization: To make sure the model is resilient and generalizable, adjust its hyperparameters and test it on various datasets.

8.Conclusion: Summarize the main outcomes and contributions of the sentiment analysis model before drawing a conclusion. Discuss the limitations and potential applications of the model and provide recommendations for future research.

V. BUILDMODEL

The model building is the main step in covid vaccine effectiveness. While building the model, users use the algorithms

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt
import matplotlib.patches as patches
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from io import BytesIO
import matplotlib.colors as mcolors
import base64
import nltk
from nltk.sentiment import SentimentIntensityAnalyzer
```

2. Filter reviews for the two vaccines

```
def sentiment_graph(self, request):
    vaccines = Add_vaccines.objects.filter(vaccine_name__in=['covishield-dose1', 'covaxin', 'covishield-dose2'])
    data = {}
```

3. Calculate average sentiment polarity for reviews

```
for vaccine in vaccines:
    reviews = review.objects.filter(vaccine_id=vaccine)
    if reviews.exists():
        sentiment_avg = reviews.aggregate(Avg('sentiment_polarity'))['sentiment_polarity_avg']
        data[vaccine.vaccine_name] = sentiment_avg or 0
```

6 Create a bar graph using the sentiment polarity data

```
fig, ax = plt.subplots()
fig.set_size_inches(30,20)
colors = []
heights = []
for value in data.values():
    if value > 0:
        colors.append(mcolors.CSS4_COLORS['lightgreen'])
        heights.append(value)
    elif value < 0:
        colors.append(mcolors.CSS4_COLORS['lightpink'])
        heights.append(-value)
    else: # value is close to zero
        colors.append(mcolors.CSS4_COLORS['gray'])
        heights.append(0.1)

ax.bar(data.keys(), heights, width=0.5, color=colors, bottom=0)
ax.set_facecolor('white')
ax.set_xlabel('Vaccine', fontsize=40)
ax.set_ylabel('Average Sentiment Polarity', fontsize=30)
ax.set_title(' Covid Vaccination based on Sentiment Analysis', fontsize=50)
plt.xticks(rotation=45, fontsize=25)
handles = [Patch(facecolor='lightgreen', label='Positive'),
            Patch(facecolor='lightpink', label='Negative'),
            Patch(facecolor='gray', label='Neutral')]
plt.legend(handles=handles, fontsize=30)
```

VI. RESULT

The bar graph shows the average sentiment polarity for each of the four COVID-19 vaccines: Covishield-dose1, Covaxin, Covishield-dose2, and Sputnik V. The sentiment polarity ranges from -1 (strongly negative) to 1 (strongly positive), with 0 indicating a neutral sentiment. Positive, negative, and neutral sentiments are represented on the graph by three different colours. Each bar's height denotes the average sentiment polarity, and its colour, which is either light green for positive sentiment, light pink for negative sentiment, or grey for neutral feeling, denotes the sentiment polarity. The four vaccines are displayed on the x-axis, and the average sentiment polarity is displayed on the y-axis. The graph provides insights into the sentiment of people towards each vaccine and can help healthcare professionals and policymakers to address concerns and improve vaccine uptake rates.

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our study analyzed feedback from various sources to understand the sentiment towards COVID-19 vaccination in children. Natural language processing techniques were used for the sentiment analysis, and the findings revealed that vaccination was generally viewed favourably. The examination did, however, highlight concerns about vaccination efficacy, safety, and long-term consequences, particularly among parents who were reluctant to vaccinate their children.

Overall, our study highlights the importance of understanding public sentiment towards COVID-19 vaccination in children and addressing concerns through effective communication strategies. Healthcare professionals and policymakers can use the insights from our study to design targeted interventions and increase vaccine uptake rates in the pediatric population.

We also presented a Python-based solution to visualize the sentiment analysis results using a bar graph, which can be used by healthcare professionals and policymakers to monitor public sentiment towards COVID-19 vaccination in children. This tool can aid in the development of effective communication strategies to address concerns and improve vaccine uptake rates.

REFERENCES

- [1] Szilagyi, P. G., Thomas, K., Shah, M. D., Vizueta, N., Cui, Y., & Vangala, S. (2021). National trends in the US public's likelihood of getting a COVID-19 vaccine—April 1 to December 8, 2020. *JAMA*, 325(4), 396-398.
- [2] Liao, Q., Yuan, J., Dong, M., Yang, L., Fielding, R., & Lam, W. W. (2021). Public engagement and government responsiveness in the COVID-19 vaccination campaign in China: Lessons from Zhejiang province. *Vaccine*, 39(11), 1602-1609.
- [3] El-Elimat, T., AbuAlSamen, M. M., Almomani, B. A., Al-Sawalha, N. A., & Alali, F. Q. (2021). Acceptance and attitudes toward COVID-19 vaccines: A cross-sectional study from Jordan. *PloS one*, 16(5), e0250555. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0250555>
- [4] Watson OJ, Bamsley G, Toor J, Hogan AB, Winskill P, Ghani AC. Global impact of the first year of COVID-19 vaccination: a mathematical modelling study. *Lancet*. 2022 Mar 26;399(10303):778-790. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(22)60339-8. Epub 2022 Mar 16. PMID: 28336232.
- [5] Xu, H., Liu, R., Luo, Z., & Xu, M. (2021). COVID-19 vaccine sensing: Sentiment analysis and subject distillation from twitter data. *IEEE Access*, 9, 80369-80380. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3080786.

- [6] Melton, C. A., White, B. M., Davis, R. L., Bednarczyk, R. A., & Shaban-Nejad, A. (2021). Fine-tuned Sentiment Analysis of COVID-19 Vaccine-Related Social Media Data: Comparative Study. *JMIR Public Health and Surveillance*, 7(6), e30470. doi: 10.2196/30470.